

**Energy Efficiency by Maneuvering Voltage 150 kV to 275 kV
(A Case Study on the Aceh Interconnection System)**

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Abstract – This research is a design and calculation of the tension maneuver of the 150 kV to 275 kV Aceh interconnection system. For the Aceh electricity network, there is a centralization of electricity generation at three points, namely Nagan Raya, Lhokseumawe and North Sumatra. This centralization causes inefficiency in the distribution of electrical energy to consumers in the Aceh region. Inefficient in the form of high power losses and low power quality levels. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to reduce power losses in the Aceh interconnection power system network and improve power quality by maneuvering the voltage from the 150kV interconnection system to the 275kV system. The Aceh interconnection power system currently operates on a 150kV system, while the 275 kV interconnection system is currently under construction for substations and transmission lines. The design and calculation of the tension maneuver of the 150 kV to 275 kV Aceh interconnection system was carried out by simulating the method using Newton Rhapson. The single line diagram of the 150 kV and 275 kV systems is simulated using the Newton Rhapson method of power quality and losses in a single line network of 150 kV and 275 kV systems. After optimizing with the addition of distributed generation, the largest power losses in the Sigli – Nagan Raya line are reduced by 802 kW or 17.8%. The total power losses that can be reduced after the Krueng Manee Geumpang distributed generation in the 150 kV Aceh system is 1.6 MW or 9.1%. The voltage improvement on all buses with the largest voltage on the bus on the Uleu Kareng bus is 2.5599 kV.

Keywords: power losses, voltage profile, maneuver voltage

Introduction

The need for electrical energy is increasing day by day in line with the increasing population and technological developments. This is clearly seen in the 150 kV Aceh interconnection system which is getting more critical day by day. For this reason, it is necessary to pay attention to the availability of this energy so that it is able to supply the electrical energy needs to all levels of Acehnese society.

The problem that occurs in the field is that the planning of an electric power system can only be carried out for the next few years and is centralized. This is due to the large investment costs required to build a large-scale electric power system all at once. Another problem is to build large-scale power plants which are generally powered by steam and gas turbines, requiring high operating costs for fuel and also high levels of air pollution.

The centralized electric power system also has an impact on the continuity of energy distribution to customers. This occurs in Aceh's 150 kV interconnection system, which is centralized in Belawan, Nagan Raya and Lhokseumawe. Among these disturbances is the interruption of energy delivery from Belawan (North Sumatra) to Aceh due to the collapse of the 150 kV tower, so that parts of Aceh have blackouts. The electricity system that is centralized in Aceh's interconnection also has an impact on the amount of wasted energy. This is due to the very long transmission network from North Sumatra to Aceh and also the amount of energy sent from North Sumatra.

Therefore, the centralization of the electric power system began to be abandoned and shifted to the decentralization of the electric power system. The decentralization of the electric power system is also known as distributed generation, namely the placement of power plants spread across every city and also in areas that experience power shortages or in load centers. The generator can function as an energy supplier during normal load, peak load or function as a standby generator which will be used in the event of a disturbance so that the reliability of the system is maintained.

The change from a decentralized system to a centralized system requires high costs and takes a long time to develop. To overcome the centralization system with large power losses can be done by maneuvering or changing the amount of voltage in the system. Manvering is only possible if the system has a substation unit with two different working voltages. The 150 KV Aceh interconnection system is currently in the process of adding the construction of a 275 kV transmission network and substation so that it is possible to maneuver the voltage from 150kV to 275kV

Materials and Methods

Research on electrical energy efficiency and distributed generation in the 150 kV Aceh interconnection system has been carried out, including:

Hasanuddin and his colleagues researched the 150 kV Aceh – North Sumatra interconnection system that efficiency would be optimal with the addition of distributed generation. However, it is not always the addition of distributed generation that will get energy efficiency, but is greatly influenced by the level of penetration of distributed generation provided in the system. it can be concluded that the optimal level of penetration in energy use is the penetration of 20% to 100% of the load carrying capacity of each substation. Optimal energy efficiency occurs at a penetration rate of 90% with a large wasted energy of 0.309 MW from the previous energy wasted before the distribution of 27.248. So that with the addition of distributed generation, it is able to minimize wasted energy by 26.939 MW or 9.7% of the 278 MW of Aceh's electricity needs. [1]

Hasanuddin and his friends conducted research on the design and calculation of power output optimization of the 150 kV Nanggroe Aceh Darussalam interconnection system which has been converted into a decentralized electricity system with the addition of distributed generation (DG) with the calculation of distributed generation output power using the genetic algorithm method resulting in reduced losses. -The largest power loss occurred in the Pangkalan Brandan – Langsa channel of 12.01 MW or 89%. [2] Hasanuddin and colleagues researched the 150 kV Aceh-North Sumatra interconnection system that efficiency would be optimal with the addition of distributed generation of the Krueng Lhok Gob Pidie Jaya hydropower type with a potential power of 2540 kW. There was the greatest reduction in power losses between the Pangkalan Brandan feeder and the Langsa feeder of 0.711 MW. The total power losses that can be reduced after the Krueng Lhok Gob distributed generation in the 150 kV Aceh system is 1.476 MW or 0.054% with a power penetration rate of 2.4 MW. [3] Hasanuddin and colleagues researched the 150 kV Aceh - North Sumatra interconnection system that efficiency would be optimal with the addition of distributed generation of solar power in the 150 kV Aceh electricity system, the greatest reduction in power losses between the Pangkalan Brandan feeder and the Langsa feeder of 2.46 MW. The total power losses that can be reduced after the Gampong Jeulikat 10 MW distributed generation in the 150 kV Aceh system is 2.234 MW or 0.08% with a distributed generation power penetration rate of 10 MW.[4] Hasanuddin and his colleagues researched the 150 kV Aceh - North Sumatra interconnection system that efficiency would be optimal with the addition of distributed generation of hydroelectric power in the 150 kV Aceh electricity system there was a reduction in the largest power losses on the Sigli - Nagan Raya line by 802 kW or 17.8%. The total power losses that can be reduced after the Krueng Manee Geumpang distributed generation in the 150 kV Aceh system is 1.6 MW or 9.1%. Voltage improvement on all buses with the largest voltage on the bus on the Uleu Kareng bus is 2.5599 kV[5].

Nazaruddin performs a power flow simulation for unbalanced load conditions on a radial distribution network. The solution to the unbalanced power flow is simulated with the ETAP application software version

7.0.0, which will be tested on the Syiah Kuala distribution network for the Banda Aceh electricity system. The results of the program simulation show that the largest power losses occur in cable 1 which connects GH Merduati with bus 1 which serves the GD SKL 2 load, namely 0.223% for phase A, 0.224% for phase B and 0.224% for phase C. The total power losses (losses) that occur in the Syiah Kuala feeder are 5 KW and 6.2 KVAR. The highest voltage drop also occurs in cable 1 which connects the Merduati Substation (GH) with bus 1 which serves the GD SKL 2 load, which is 0.31% for phase A, 0.32% for phase B and 0.32% for phase C. [6] Adib Gustian conducts power flow simulation at PT. Asia Pacific Fibers Tbk Kendal, with lumped load characteristics. The power flow analysis begins with calculating the active power and reactive power at each node (bus) installed, the load on the transformer, the load on the line or conductor, the value of power loss (losses), the system voltage drop, and the flow of power on the installed electric power system network. From the results of the calculation of the power flow assisted by the ETAP (Electrical Transient Analyzer Program) program, it can be concluded that the electrical network system is good. The results obtained are the difference between active power loss and reactive power loss on Bus Load 4 is too large. While the voltage drop still meets the standards according to the results of the Text Report on ETAP. [7] Ali Supriyadi performed a power flow simulation using the Gauss-Seidel method and the Newton Raphson method. The Newton Raphson method reaches a convergent value faster so that the iteration process takes less time. By using ETAP, it can be seen quickly what actions must be known, from the results of the analysis to improve the over excited state of generator 2, the addition of a capacitor on the bus that is directly connected to generator 2 is 21 Mvar.[8] This research is a development of the above studies, namely the efficiency of energy transmission in the Aceh interconnection transmission network with voltage maneuvers from 150kV to 275kV.

This research is intended to observe the efficiency of energy distribution in the 150 kV Aceh interconnection system. The stages of the research carried out are as follows;

1. Collecting data on Aceh's 150 kV interconnection system regarding network parameters, power requirements of each GI, and the output power of each generator. The function of the GI is to reduce the voltage from 150 kV to 20 kV by using a step down transformer with various capacities including 30 MVA with a ratio of 150/20 kV. Electrical energy from the primary distribution voltage of 20 kV is then distributed to consumers in the PT PLN area of Aceh. The distance of power transfer from the Pangkalan Brandan Substation to Banda Aceh through the High Voltage Air Line (SUTET) circuit is 471.22 km which causes a lot of wasted energy in the form of power losses and large voltage drops.
2. Calculating network parameters in units The line impedance is calculated based on the type and size of the conductor used between substations multiplied by the length/distance between the substations.
3. Designing a single line diagram for the 150kV and 275kV Aceh interconnection system in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Single Line Diagram of the 150 kV Aceh System

4. Entering network parameters, generators and substations data from tables 1 to 3.

Table 1. Network Parameters

SUBSTATIONS	Cable Size (240)		Cable Length (KM)	R (OHM)	X (OHM)	Impedance (OHM)
	R (OHM/KM)	X (OHM/KM)				
GI SIGLI to GI BIREUN	0,137	0,397	198,4	13,5904	39,3824	13,5904 + j393824
GI LHOKEUMAWE to GI LANGSA	0,137	0,397	128,49	17,60313	51,01053	17,6031 + j51,0105
GI IDI to GI LHOKEUMAWE	0,137	0,397	82,19	11,2600	32,62943	11,26 + j32,6294
GI IDI to GI LANGSA	0,137	0,397	46,3	6,3431	18,3811	6,3431 + j18,3811
GI LANGSA to GI TUALANG CUT	0,137	0,397	24,12	3,3044	9,5756	3,3044 + j9,5756
GI LHOKEUMAWE to GI BIREUN	0,137	0,397	122,6	8,3981	24,3361	8,3981 + j24,3361
GI LANGSA to GI PANGKALAN BRANDAN	0,137	0,397	156,54	10,7230	31,07319	10,7230 + j31,0732
GI SIGLI to GI BANDA ACEH	0,137	0,397	183,3	12,55605	36,38505	12,5561 + j36,3851
GI SIGLI to GI	0,137	0,397	346	23,7010	68,6810	23,7010 +

NAGAN RAYA							j68,6810
GI BANDA							
ACEH to GI	0,137	0,397	31,2	4,2744	12,3864	4,2744 +j	12,3864
JANTHO							
GI JANTHO TO							
GI SIGLI	0,137	0,397	60,39	8,2734	23,9748	8,2734 +j	23,9748
GI							
LHOKSEUMAWE							
TO GI PANTON	0,137	0,397	30	4,1100	11,91	4,1100 +j	11,91
LABU							
GI PANTON							
LABU TO GI IDI	0,137	0,397	50,52	6,9212	20,0564	6,9212 +	20,0564

Table 2. Substations Load

No	Substations	MW	MVAR
1.	Banda Aceh	68,9	6,7
2.	Jantho	8,3	1,3
3.	Sigli	43	6,5
4.	Bireun	22,8	7,3
5.	Lhokseumawe	32,3	6,1
6.	Panton Labu	26,1	6,1
7.	Idi	18,8	3,7
8.	Langsa	24,9	8,3
9.	Tualang Cut	25	5,1
10.	Nagan Raya	11,3	3,7
11	Takengon	21,9	7,7
12	Ulee Kareng	0,22	-0,06
13	PJB/ARUN	29,8	4,1
14	Samalanga	11,3	2,6
15	Meulaboh	29,5	4,4
16	Blang Pidie	18	3
17	Krueng Raya	1,49	0,43

Table 3. Generators

No	Generators	Units	Capacity(MW)
1	System Sumut	Swing Bus	Swing Bus
2	PLTMG Arun PJB	4	184
3	PLTU Nagan Raya	2	220
4	PLTMG Arun Peaker	13	13x18

5. Performing power flow simulation using Newton Rhapsod method on 150kV and 275kV interconnection systems Aceh.
6. Analysis of system power flow with 150kV and 275kV voltage maneuvers to find out improvements in power distribution efficiency in the network and power quality to customers. The simulation results of the system power flow with the 150kV and 275kV voltage maneuvers were analyzed against several variables including:
 - a. Losses on the 150kV transmission line between buses before maneuvering the voltage to 275kV

- b. Electrical energy efficiency in the 150kV transmission network between buses by comparing before and after the voltage maneuver to 275kV.
- c. Voltage Profile between before and after the voltage maneuver to 275kV.

Data collection

Power Loss in the Feeder

The power losses that occur in each of the 150 kV Aceh interconnection power system feeders before and after the 275 kV voltage maneuver can be explained as follows:

Figure 2 shows the power losses in the channel where before the voltage maneuver was carried out to 275 kV, the largest power losses occurred in the Sigli - Nagan Raya channel of 4506.7 kW. While the smallest losses occurred in the Krueng Raya – Ule Kareng channel of 0.3 kW. This is due to the length of the channel and the magnitude of the load on each substation. The total power losses that occur are 17214 kW

Figure 2. Power loss 150 kV .

Figure 3 shows the power losses in the line after maneuvering the voltage to 275 kV, the biggest power losses occur in the Sigli - Nagan Raya line of 1924.8 KW. While the smallest losses occurred in the Krueng Raya – Ule Kareng channel of 0.1 kW. The total power losses that occur after optimization are 6881.3 kW. This means that there has been a decrease in power losses of 10333 kW or 60%.

Figure 3. Power loss 275 kV

Figure 4 shows a comparison of power losses in the line before and after the voltage maneuver, the largest reduction in power losses occurs in the Sigli - Nagan Raya line by 2581.9 kW or 57%.

Figure 4. Power loss comparison voltage maneuver

Results

Voltage Profile of the Aceh Electricity System

From the graph of Figure 5 it can be seen that the Voltage Profile when maneuvering the voltage to 275 kV, the highest voltage increase of 14.7 kV is still within the 10% tolerance limit, which is 27.5 kV which occurs on the Krueng Raya bus

Figure 5. Voltage Profile 150 and 275 kV

The voltage drop shift from the 150 kV system to 275 kV as shown in Figure 6 is seen in the 150 kV system where all bus voltages are below the nominal voltage of 150 kV. Meanwhile, in the 275 kV voltage system, only 5 of the 17 buses have a voltage below the nominal voltage of 275 kV.

Figure 6. Voltage Profile Comparison 150 and 275 kV

Aceh Electricity System Power Factor

From the graph of Figure 7 it can be seen that the power factor when maneuvering the voltage to 275 kV experienced a very large decrease on the Ulee Kareng bus from 94.8 to 52.1 while for the other buses there was no significant change and was still within the tolerance limit of 0.8. except for the Bireun and Banda Aceh buses 0.784 and 0.787.

Figure 7. Power Factor 150 and 275 kV

Conclusion

After conducting research on voltage maneuvers from 150 to 275 kV on the 150 kV Aceh interconnection system, several conclusions can be drawn including: Power losses in the line before the voltage maneuver to 275 kV, the largest power losses occurred in the Sigli - Nagan Raya line of 4506.7 kW. While the smallest losses occurred in the Krueng Raya – Ule Kareng channel of 0.3 kW. The total power losses that occur are 17214 kW. The power losses in the line after maneuvering the

voltage to 275 kV, the largest power losses occurred in the Sigli - Nagan Raya line of 1924.8 kW. While the smallest losses occurred in the Krueng Raya – Ule Kareng channel of 0.1 kW. The total power losses that occur after optimization are 6881.3 kW. This means that there has been a decrease in power losses of 10333 kW or 60%. Shrinkage of power losses after the voltage maneuver is 10333 kW or 60%. The largest reduction in power losses occurred in the Sigli – Nagan Raya channel of 2581.9 kW or 57%. Voltage Profile at the time of maneuvering the voltage to 275 kV, the highest voltage increase of 14.7 kV is still within the 10% tolerance limit, which is 27.5 kV. Power factor when maneuvering the voltage to 275 kV experienced a very large decrease on the Ulee Kareng bus from 94.8 to 52.1.

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